

The Influence of Agile Leadership and Organizational Culture on Innovative Work Behavior Mediated by Talent Management

(Study at Pt. Bintang Sampurna in Central Jakarta)

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Abstract:- This research aims to analyze the factors that influence innovative work behavior at PT. Perfect Star in Central Jakarta. The population of this study were employees from PT. Bintang Perfect in Central Jakarta with a sample size of 86 employees. The data analysis method uses Structural Equation Model-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS). Research result find that Agile leadership matters positive to management talent. Agile leadership matters positive to behavior Work innovative. Management talent influential positive to behavior Work innovative. Culture organization influential positive to management talent. Culture organization influential positive to behavior Work innovative. Management talent role mediate influence agile leadership towards Behavior Work Innovative, and Management talent role mediate influence Culture Organize to Behavior Work Innovative at PT. Perfect Star in Central Jakarta.

Keywords:- Agile Leadership, Culture Organization, Management Talent, Behavior Work Innovative, Sem Pls.

I. INTRODUCTION

Getting started In 2020, Indonesia was shocked with exists pandemic called covid-19 which has an impact No just on health public but also sectors other. The situation that occurred No only cause death of people but also conditions country's economy. Company faced challenge and try find way for them endure life. Many decisions have to be made taken, like close business temporary and cutting or apply no leave paid to employees they. Business world face a situation where Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and Ambiguity (VUCA). World dynamics during the Covid-19 pandemic have resulted in the term VUCA begins experience change become BANI. BANI is abbreviation from Brittle, Anxiety, Non-Linear and Incomprehensible this is more appropriate to define circumstances increasingly economic and social _ is at the peak instability . This situation causes company must thinking about strategy is not just to survive but also do a number of adjustment to situation . So that they can maintain and grow, if company No can face and handle situation that occurred they Possible face difficulties and in the end will closed (Sulistiyawati, 2021).

During pandemic, letter news and magazines are the hardest hit. Because it increases Work from home (work from home), sales decreased, and readers switch to online media. Even IKEA stopped publish catalog to save cost operational . The digital printing industry has also been greatly affected by the Lockdown due to public stop visit shops , bars, restaurants and hotels. Also, printing commercial like Bulletins , manual books and leaflets suffered greatly . Decline this radical demand makes a number of provider printing service closes (printgraphicmagz.com, 2023)

PT Bintang Perfect , which is located in the area Dam Hilir (Benhil) Central Jakarta, is one of them company Digital and offset printing are affected impact COVID-19 pandemic and BANI's current condition. Tallo, 2021). Every problem own solution, and every crisis bring opportunity. There will be point sunny where we are can get up and face difficulty. BANI is not " the end of the world " for you individual, country, nation, company, or organization whatever. He is phase new in civilization man. Change civilization that occurred after the COVID-19 pandemic can seen in modern context, as demonstrated by the increase penetration digital technology, robotics, and the internet, which is changing method relation social regulated (Ahmad, 2023).

Responding matter the Perfect Star management do steps adapt and adjust to be able to still stay in the middle conditions that are not uncertain, adjustments are made is the one before pandemic company operate for 24 hours change become only one shift (8 working hours), Automatic Because exists there are many policies affected employees, Starting from enter Work in a way alternating, reduced working hours, up to with offer paid leave specifically (employees at home But still get his rights like salary 25% - 50% as well BPJS health and employment payments) and offers pension early for employees who have worked for a long time. Apart from doing adjustments to operating hours Work management and leadership the company is also thinking about method how to keep it Can survive and compete with competitors similar business. Competition increasing effort strict require every perpetrator business must capable think about innovation Work What just have to carried out so that the business is carried out still survive and experience development (Sinulingga, 2021).

Behavior Work Perfect Star innovation do is with method optimizing role from the web to print or online print platform that Bintang Perfect have so that Can optimizing income company from customers who don't Can come to the store because constrained restrictions at the start Covid-19 pandemic. Not only That's where the behavior ends Work Perfect Star innovation do it to stay Can endure is with do various activity collaboration with various party such as assisted MSMEs Sinarmas land, academics (Binus Campus, Lasalle College, Trisakti, UMN, Sampoerna and schools IPB Vocational) and practitioners like IKAPI (Indonesian Publishers Association) in the era of pandemic and disruption like Now face Lots very problems in the field printing or publishing book physical (Pujianto, 2021).

To survive in a growing market competitive, company must capable develop behavior innovative work. This is due to competence strong business, influence environment, and power competitive. Leadership, culture organization, management talent, and compensation is a number of factor affecting behavior Work innovative employees, according to study previously (Purwanto et al., 2020; Esha & Dwipayani , 2021; Abadi & Nur, 2022).

To find out what factors influence innovative work behavior at PT. Bintang Perfect, Central Jakarta, a pre-survey was conducted on 30 employees who were still working. The survey results can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1 Pre-Survey Results of Factors that Influence Innovative Work Behavior at PT. Perfect Star, Central Jakarta

No	Question	Answer		Total
		Yes	No	
1	Does agile leadership influence your innovative work behavior?	27 (90%)	3 (10%)	30 (100%)
2	Does organizational culture influence your innovative work behavior?	25 (83,3%)	5 (16,7%)	30 (100%)
3	Does the talent management / training you receive have an influence on your innovative work behavior?	22 (73,3%)	8 (26,7%)	30 (100%)
4	Does the compensation you receive influence your innovative work behavior?	20 (66,7%)	10 (33%)	30 (100%)
5	Does your work status influence your innovative work behavior?	18 (60%)	12 (40%)	30 (100%)

Based on the results of a pre-survey conducted on employees working at PT. Perfect Star is agile leadership at 90%, organizational culture at 83.3%, and talent management/ training at 73.3%. Based on this data very important factor in company is agile leadership. A leader must own strong understanding about How something organization will develop in the future taking into account changes that will happened outside environment company.

Based on the explanations above, to complete problems research, then important to study on “Influence Agile Leadership and Culture Organization to Behavior Work Innovative Mediated by Management Talent in the company printing PT. Perfect Star in Central Jakarta.”.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Agile Leadership

According to Joineir and Joseiph (2007), agile leadership (Agilei Leiaideirship) is the ability of a leader to make wise and effective decisions in a complex, unpredictable and quickly changing environment.

Agile leadership is ability a leader to create wise and effective decisions in complex environment, no uncertain and changing with fast. According to Joner and Joseph (2007), agile leadership is ability a leader to learn style leadership new and new flexible replace style leadership traditional in attempt to speed things up response to dynamic and changing circumstances (Meyer & Meijers, 2017) To create related experience with mark for all stakeholders, agile leadership enables flexible and adaptive strategies that are based on internal and external changes (Chatwani, 2019). Wardani et al . (2023)

The results of research by Akkaya, B. and Tabak, A. (2020) show that the manager pointed out agile leadership directly or didn't get it straight away increase ability dynamic company with make environment profitable, motivating organization employee with thought open, stylish life innovative, and thoughtful open. Besides, leader create the right environment in which employees can share knowledge them and develop their ideas.

With So, you can concluded that Agile leadership makes it possible leadership that has skill in guide team and enable team for for learn values from customer. This team has Lots expertise, flexibility, and speed can help organization become more successful and ready to face challenge currently (Kusumawati, DA2021).

- H1 : Agile will positive face face Manage me n Talenta.
- H2 : leadership be rpe ngaru h positive face face Behavior To rja Innovative .

B. Organizational Culture

Everyone who participates in something organization must understand principles and values that become base culture organization (Robbins and Judge, 2008). They also said that culture organization is system or values adopted meaning _ shared by members organization , which created it unique and become characteristic typically .

In line with the theory put forward by Taurisa et al. (2012), a strong and positive organizational culture describes employee working conditions; in talent management, a culture that encourages innovation can encourage employees to create new ideas. In this context, an organizational culture that supports learning and development can help build quality employees through training and development programs. An organizational culture that promotes collaboration and teamwork, also supports talent management by facilitating the exchange of knowledge and experience between employees. A strong organizational culture has a big influence on the behavior of its members.

Based on research conducted by Ni'matusholikha, R. N. A. (2021) entitled "The influence of organizational culture on innovative work behavior is mediated by the Islamic work ethic" shows the results that organizational culture has a direct influence on innovative work behavior.

- H4: Organizational culture has a positive effect on talent management
- H5: Organizational culture has a positive effect on innovative work behavior.

C. Talent Management

Talent or talent according to (Lyria, R. K. 2015) refers to the sum of a person's abilities; including his intrinsic talents, skills, knowledge, experience, intelligence, judgment, attitude, character and drive. This definition will be used in this research to refer to employees who have special abilities to perform certain tasks. Meanwhile, Talent Management is an active management system used by organizations to identify, capture, utilize, develop, grow and maintain employee talent for the benefit of the work team and the organization at large (Lyria, R. K. 2015).

According to Pella and Inayati (2011), " Management talent is a process to ensure something company fill in position key future leaders and supporting positions the company's core competencies (unique skills and high strategic value)."

Give mark to customer is objective main a skilled businessman. Agile leadership is the ability to influence others and change something (Sanatgar et al., 2017).

Researcher Not yet find theory or study previously used it management talent as a connecting mediating variable superiority competitiveness and agile leadership. They hope this research will produce findings new to the field knowledge research. It is also hoped that this finding can be applied in a way practical.

- H6: Human Resource Management mediates the influence of Agile Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior.
- H7: Talent management plays a mediating role in the influence of Organizational Culture on Innovative Work Behavior.

D. Innovative Work Behavior

According to Messman and Mulder (2011), innovation is way to solve problem or repair situation currently with make product or a useful new process, then developed and implemented in environment Work certain. to produce behavior creative and inventive work innovation . Innovative work behavior is often associated with creativity; this includes the implementation and creativity of ideas (De Jong & Hartog, 2010). According to Nyoman and Ardana (2020), innovative work behavior is the attitude of incorporating, proposing and implementing new methods, ideas and products into their work environment. To maintain the company's competitiveness and increase employee productivity, creative work behavior is very important. Hammond, according to Widiastuti, (2020).

➤ Based on these Theories, the Framework for this Research is as Follows:

Fig 1 Framework Thinking

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses method quantitative, using Partial Least Square Structural Equation Model (PLS SEM) approach. Hypothesis study tested with the Partial Least Square (Smart-PLS) program version 3.0. Data will checked using two models. The measurement model (Outer Model) connects indicator with variable latent, while the structural model (Inner Model) connects between latent variable.

This research uses variable Agile Leadership (X1), Culture Organization (X2), Management Talent (Z), and Behavior Work Innovative (Y2). This research uses non-probability purposive sampling method to collect data. Population this research is employees who work at a digital printing company in central Jakarta as many as 86 employees still . Saturated samples were used for sampling, which included 30 employees, questionnaires with a Likert scale.

- H3: Talent Management has a positive effect on Innovative Work Behavior

IV. RESULTS

A. Outer Model

Is how every indicator interact with variable latent explained by this model. In other words, the outer model can explain How latent variables and indicators interact One each other. Construct reliability, convergent validity and discriminant validity values were used to produce the outer model.

Fig 2 Path Diagram Outer Loading

➤ Test Result Convergent Validity

Factor value shelter on latent variables and indicators called exam validity convergent. This evaluation process is carried out to verify validity of each variable. All indicators for each variable own mark burden outside or burden bigger factor of 0.5, which means that all over valid indicator, as shown by the route diagram of the measurement model in figure 4. Therefore, the condition validity convergent has fulfilled by the research model, which means that every indicator can used to measure the construct.

Additionally, validity convergent can tested with look at AVE (Average Variation Extracted). If the construct AVE value is more than 0.5, then construct fulfil validity convergent.

Table 2 AVE Value Results

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Organizational culture	0,645
Agile Leadership	0,719
Talent Management	0,608
Innovative Work Behavior	0,654

Entire variable own validity discriminant, as shown by the table, with AVE value is more than 0.5.

➤ Test Result Discriminant Validity

Validity test results discriminant based on Fornell Lackers study is as follows:

Table 3 Fornell and Larcker Test Results

	Organizational culture	Agile Leadership	Talent Management	Innovative Work Behavior
Organizational culture	0.803			
Agile Leadership	0.534	0.848		
Talent Management	0.573	0.549	0.780	
Innovative Work Behavior	0.659	0.789	0.706	0.809

The result show that every construct own greater value _ rather than correlation between constructs in models. Thus, it can be said that each construct is discriminantly valid.

➤ Test result Reliability

If value combined reliability questionnaire is more than 0.70, then questionnaire is instrument research that can reliable and consistent (Hair et al., 2016)

Table 4 Reliability Results

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Ket.
Organizational culture	0.959	0.970	0.962	0.645	Reliable
Agile Leadership	0.934	0.935	0.947	0.719	Reliable
Talent Management	0.957	0.958	0.961	0.608	Reliable
Innovative Work Behavior	0.867	0.869	0.904	0.654	Reliable

The result show that all over variable study own mark composite reliability is more than 0.7 and AVE is more than 0.5, meaning the data is reliable and can be An inner model test was carried out .

B. Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

Inner model testing can be done seen through mark coefficient determination of R-Square (R²), effect size (F²), and Q-Square predictive relevance (Q²). While , level significance coefficient track used for testing hypothesis ie predict connection between latent variable .

➤ R-Square Value Test Results (R²)

Coefficient determination R Square (R²) shows how much big variable exogenous explain variable its endogenous.

Table 5 R Square Value (R²)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Talent Management	0.411	0.397
Innovative Work Behavior	0.757	0.748

The result that is explain explain Agile Leadership, Culture Organization in a way simultaneous influence with currently variable Management Talent that is amounted to 0.411 (41.1%) whereas the remaining 58.9% is influenced by other factors outside the model. Meanwhile, Agile Leadership, Culture Organization, and Management Talent in a way simultaneous influence with currently variable Behavior Work Innovative that is amounted to 0.757 (75.7%) whereas the remaining 24.3% is influenced by other factors outside the model.

➤ Goodness of Fix Index (GoF)

Purpose of doing Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) testing is to validate performance combined between the measurement model (outer model) and the structural model (inner model) obtained through calculation as follows:

• Table 6: GoF Value

$$GoF = \sqrt{AVE} \times R^2$$

$$GoF = \sqrt{0.537} \times 0.737$$

$$GoF = \sqrt{0.396}$$

$$GoF = 0.629$$

Note:

$$AVE = (0.512 + 0.508 + 0.538 + 0.591) / 4 = 0.537$$

$$R^2 = (0.780 + 0.695) / 2 = 0.737$$

The results of the Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) calculation show value 0.629. According to Ghazali (2016), value GoF small = 0.1, GoF medium = 0.25 and GoF lag = 0.36. Based on results the so can concluded that performance combined between the measurement model (outer model) and the structural model (inner model) . whole is the medium because the Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) value is more than 0.25 (medium GoF scale).

➤ Testing Hypothesis

In this research, hypothesis One direction with 5% significance, also known as tolerance error $\alpha = 0.05$, used.

Fig 3 Path Diagram Path Coefficient & T-Statistics Model Structural (Inner Model)

Table 6 Results of Direct & Indirect Hypothesis Testing

Relationship Between Constructs (Direct Influence)	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Hypothesis
Agile Leadership-> Innovative Work Behavior	0.508	0.504	0.062	8.162	0.000	Accepted
Agile Leadership -> Talent Management	0.340	0.329	0.098	3.465	0.001	Accepted
Organizational culture-> Innovative Work Behavior	0.212	0.211	0.070	3.044	0.002	Accepted
Organizational culture-> Talent Management	0.392	0.396	0.080	4.877	0.000	Accepted
Talent Management-> Innovative Work Behavior	0.306	0.308	0.074	4.105	0.000	Accepted
Indirect Relationships	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Ket.
Talent Management-> Agile Leadership-> Innovative Work Behavior	0.104	0.103	0.040	2.626	0.009	Accepted
Talent Management-> Innovative Work Behavior	0.120	0.124	0.045	2.645	0.008	Accepted

V. DISCUSSION

A. H1: *The Influence of Agile Leadership on Innovative Work Behavior*

Based on results study found that agile leadership matters positive and significant to management talent at PT. Perfect Star, Central Jakarta. Demonstrated Agile Leadership with characteristic features creativity, reactivity, ability adapt, effort learning and handling stress if seen from indicators that measure Agile leadership ie ability adapt and attitude reactive it has leader company in face all conditions that are not uncertain and challenging existing business Now require every leader must own agile/ fast attitude in act and take something despair with precise and efficient. A Agile leaders must too Can give good example to his subordinates Apart from that, you also need to be an agile leader Can convey idea or his ideas in form clear vision and mission so that's all Can achieved by all management talent in the company. Study previously by Kaok, M., Yusuf, RM, and Dewi, ARS (2019) found that style leadership influence management talent with Good. However, researchers Not yet find theory or study previously about related agile leadership with management talent.

B. H2: *The Effect of Agile Leadership on Talent Management*

Applied agile leadership leader company PT. Perfect Star of course proven implemented effectively in the environment work, for example when happen pandemic beginning In 2019, the leadership immediately took over attitude with optimizing the Perfect Star Online Print platform have to be able to answer problem or the challenge at that time was mobility public limited, apart from that with exists policy Only then are employees also involved in providing suggestions or ideas for how to do it Work more optimally and innovatively from difficult times like that. The employees many are motivated with attitude leaders who give employees " freedom " to create or create something useful or useful for customers. Study Fahrurrobi , N., Ihsan, M., Rahmawati, I., and Lestari, H. (2020). that state that style leadership impact positive on behavior innovative in place Work . However, researchers Not yet find theory or study previously about related agile leadership with behavior innovative in place Work.

C. H3: *Influence Management Talent to Behavior Work Innovative*

Based on the results of this research, it shows directly that talent management has a positive influence on the innovative work behavior of employees at PT. Bintang Perfect, if researchers observe the application of talent management implemented by the company which has an impact on employees' innovative work behavior, it is the training and development program that is routinely held by the company, employees will be assessed by their direct superiors before carrying out training and development that is appropriate to their job description. Employees' ability to innovate has been shown to increase with talent management, which includes the identification, development and retention of talented employees. Innovative work behavior increases due to well-integrated training and development programs, management support for creative concepts, and fair reward systems. The discussion of research results also includes suggestions for PT companies. Bintang Perfect so that it continues to develop and

can compete with competitors in the same business. It is hoped that management will continue to improve talent management programs, provide employees with opportunities to develop, and build an environment that supports innovation. The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Khan, Z. A. (2019) which states that Talent Management improves and has a positive influence on employee Innovative Work Behavior. However, the results of this study are not in line with research conducted by Dzimbiri, G. L., & Molefakgotla, A. (2021) where the research results show that talent management practices do not contribute to the innovative work behavior of registered nurses in public hospitals in Malawi.

D. H4: *Influence Culture Organization to Management Talent*

Based on results This research shows directly that culture organization own positive influence to management talents of employees at PT. Perfect Star, Apparently culture Organization is critical to success management talent. Culture organization must upgraded to support management talent . Leader company it is recommended to understand principles valued by employees they make an environment that supports new ideas, and encourages all over team to help manage talent. This company is welcoming change and start repair culture organization. To help management talents, them create training programs, involve employee in taking decisions, and improve communication. As a result, results this study did not only give information new but also brings change positive for company. This company relies on culture supporting organization management effective talent to overcome market changes and yield sustainable innovation. A previous study by Zubir and Djati (2017) found that culture organization influence management talent and performance employees in the company studied.

E. H5: *5. Influence Culture Organization to Behavior Work Innovative*

Based on the results of this research, it shows directly that organizational culture has a positive influence on the innovative work behavior of employees at PT. Perfect Star. To continue to grow, companies must understand how their organizational culture influences the innovative work behavior of their employees. It turns out that an organizational culture that encourages experimentation and creative problem solving greatly influences the extent to which employees feel encouraged to behave innovatively. Researchers interviewed employees to hear compelling stories about how collective support and freedom of expression fostered new ideas. On the other hand, employees who work in departments with a rigid hierarchical structure tend to be less encouraged to develop new ideas.

The results of this research provide suggestions on how to strengthen an organizational culture that supports innovation. Organizational leaders are encouraged to improve communications and design programs that reward creative ideas and make the entire team feel that they are contributing to the formation of an innovative culture. With renewed vigor, the company initiated concrete actions to improve corporate culture. They establish policies that support the free expression of ideas, allow for creative discussion, and create training

programs. Therefore, an organizational culture that supports innovative work behavior is increasingly taking root in every part of the company. The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Hamid, D., & Dairmaz, O. (2021). which states that organizational culture has an influence and support from colleagues has a positive effect on innovative work behavior in employees.

F. H6: Management Talent Mediate Influence Agile Leadership towards Behavior Work Innovative

Agile leadership helps manage talent in company. It turns out a proactive, visionary and adaptive leader can push team management talent to create supportive programs and policies growth employee. However, what is more interesting is findings that management talent works as a strong mediator between Agile leadership and behavior Work innovative employee. Policy management good talent can connect vision leader with creativity and innovation employee. The results of this research provide better understanding and direction for organization to continue strengthen management talent and leadership as source sustainable innovation. The results of this study are consistent with research conducted by Kaok, M., Yusuf, RM, & Dewi, ARS (2019) which states that style leadership influential on talent management and talent management influential positive to development employee. In line with the research Yumhi, Y. (2021). Also stated that By simultaneous and partial, leadership transformational and transactional, behavior work, and innovation Work can used as variable predictor performance task.

G. H7: Management Talent Mediate Influence Culture Organization to Behavior Work Innovative

Researcher find that management talent works as a strong mediator between culture organization and behavior Work innovative, with see How culture organization push Work equality, diversity, and courage. Research result No only become the basis for better understanding, but also becoming guide to create environment supportive work _ innovation and creativity. The results of this study are consistent with research conducted by Ni'matuisholikha, RNA (2021). That state that results this research shows that culture organization influential directly towards innovative work behavior.

VI. CONCLUSION

➤ *Conclusions of this Research is :*

Agile leadership matters positive to Management Talent, Agile Leadership matters positive to Behavior Work Innovative, Cultural Organization influential positive to Management talent, culture Organization influential positive to Behavior Work Innovative, Management Talent influential positive to Behavior Work Innovative, Management talent role mediate influence Agile leadership towards Behavior Work Innovative, as well Management talent role mediate influence Culture Organization to Behavior Work Innovative.

➤ *Suggestion*

In order to increase behavior Work innovative employees at PT. Perfect Star There is a number of things that can be attempted to be done, based on results study the strongest dimension is look for support for ideas, Communicate the

company's Vision and Mission: Ensure all employee understand vision and mission company about innovation as well as To create culture organization being viewed from the strongest dimension, viz oriented results. Culture nice work possible employees to work hard with accuracy so that they can reduce error and reduce risk. Conscientious employees can too create encouraging environment creativity and innovation, as well important achievement objective organization.

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